

Keywords: long jump, video computer analysis, computer modelling, centre of gravity, biomechanical analysis.

Research Relevance. Long jump is one of the main disciplines of athletics, presented at the Olympic Games, and is quite well studied in sports science [4,5,7,8,9,10,12,13,14]. Researchers employ various approaches to study sports movements, including optical markers, inertial sensors, and AI-powered processing of video recordings [1,2,3,6,12,13,14,15]. However, using these methods involves certain costs and is not possible during competitions.

This is why researchers and coaches mainly use video computer analysis of regular video recordings to study long jumps, which is often complicated by the low quality of the recording, the low frame rate or the movement of the camera. It is especially difficult to analyse video recordings of jumps taken during competitions.

The result of the long jump depends on many parameters: the take-off velocity of the athlete's centre of gravity and the angle of the take-off velocity vector to the horizontal, the coordinates of the centre of gravity at the moments of take-off and landing, aerodynamic parameters, and others [4,5,7,8,9,10,12,13,14].

Video-computer analysis enables the reconstruction of the athlete's centre of gravity trajectory and the identification of parameters that determine the jump result, which in turn helps the coach understand the athlete's weaknesses and strengths. In our article, we discuss a new method of video-computer analysis of the long jump when the trajectory of the centre of gravity cannot be reconstructed by conventional methods.

Despite the existing difficulties, analysing the long jump technique is of great importance during the training of both amateur and professional athletes.

In this context, simple, fast, and inexpensive methods of biomechanical analysis are of particular interest.

Research aim and objectives. The primary objective of our research is to develop a straightforward and cost-effective method for computer analysis of video recordings of long jumps captured during competitions and training.

Research Methods and Organization. Our method is based on the standard model of long jump, which is presented in the work of Linthorn et al. [7]. To process the videos, we used a free video computer analysis program called Kinovea.

Fig. 1. The standard model of the long jump [7].

The standard model of the long jump is shown in Fig. 1, where the following partial distances are defined:

L_0 : Take-off distance: the horizontal distance between the start line and the vertical projection of the centre of gravity at the moment of take-off;

L_1 : Flight distance: the horizontal distance covered by the athlete's centre of mass when the athlete moves freely in the air (feet do not touch the ground);

L_2 : Landing distance: the horizontal distance between the vertical projection of the gravity centre and the athlete's heels when the heels touch the sand.

The distance L_1 constitutes more than 85% of the total jump distance and therefore determines the final result. It can be said that L_1 , and along with it the jump result, is determined by the following factors: the initial velocity of the athlete's centre of gravity V_0 , its angle to the horizontal α , the positions of the centre of gravity at the take-off moment - (L_0, h_0) and the moment of landing - ($L - L_2, h_2$), and the effect of air drag.

Suppose we know the jump result L , the duration of the jump flight phase T , and the parameters L_0, h_0, L_2, h_2 describing the positions of the athlete's centre of gravity at the moments of take-off and landing. In that case, we can calculate the horizontal and vertical projections of the initial velocity $V_0 - V_{0x}$ and V_{0y} , its angle to the horizontal α , and the maximum height H_{max} of the athlete's overall centre of gravity using the following formulas:

$$\begin{aligned} V_{0x} &= (L - L_0 - L_2 + d)/T, \\ V_{0y} &= (h_2 - h_0 + g \cdot T^2/2)/T, \\ \alpha &= \arctan(V_{0y} / V_{0x}), \\ H_{max} &= h_0 + V_{0y}^2 / g - V_{0y}^2 / (2 \cdot g), \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where t is the time from take-off, $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$ is the acceleration due to gravity, and d is the correction for the result of the jump caused by the force of air drag (for highly qualified jumpers, $d \approx 0.1 \text{ m}$ [4,5,10]).

To test our method, we analysed the jumps of five Olympic champions who won the championship at the Olympic Games in 2004, 2008, 2012, 2016, and 2020. Video recordings of the jumps can be found on YouTube [11]. The athletes' data are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Heights, weights, and long jump results of selected athletes.

Athlete's name	Event	Jump result L(m)	Height (m)	Weight (kg)
Dwight Phillips	Athens 2004	8.59	1.80	82
Irving Saladino	Beijing 2008	8.34	1.83	70
Greg Rutherford	London 2012	8.31	1.88	92
Jeff Henderson	Rio 2016	8.38	1.83	81
Miltiadis Tentoglou	Tokyo 2020	8.41	1.85	75

Photos of selected athletes are presented in Fig. 2. From large copies of these images, we can find the proportions and lengths of body parts of selected athletes, which are then used in Kinovea for frame scaling.

Fig. 2. Photos of athletes selected for analysis. From left to right: Dwight Phillips, Irving Saladino, Greg Rutherford, Jeff Henderson, Miltiadis Tentoglou.

Videos are recorded with a moving camera, the frame rate is 25 frames per second, and the video has a low resolution, so determining the trajectory of the athlete's centre of gravity directly from the video is impossible.

So we used a different approach: using Kinovea, we found the duration of the flight phase T for each jump, and processed the frames showing the moments of take-off and landing, from which we determined the coordinates of the athletes' centres of gravity at the moments of take-off and landing - (L_0, h_0) and (L_2, h_2). To determine the location of the centre of gravity, the Kinovea human body model tool was applied.

Then, using formulas (1), we calculated the parameters V_{0x} , V_{0y} , α , and H_{max} . A schematic view of the process of video-computer analysis is presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. A schematic view of the process of video-computer analysis.

Research Results Analysis. Fig. 4 shows the results of the analysis of Greg Rutherford's body positions during take-off and landing performed in Kinovea. Calculated parameters of long jumps are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Fig. 4. The analysis of Greg Rutherford's body positions at the moments of take-off and landing.

Table 2. The table below presents the values of T , L_0 , h_0 , L_2 and h_2 found by analysis in Kinovea.

Athlete's name	T (ms)	L_0 (m)	h_0 (m)	L_2 (m)	h_2 (m)
Dwight Phillips	880	0.23	1.17	0.58	0.41

Irving Saladino	880	0.28	1.22	0.72	0.64
Greg Rutherford	840	0.3	1.28	0.51	0.44
Jeff Henderson	880	0.14	1.23	0.54	0.59
Miltiadis Tentoglou	880	0.33	1.11	0.53	0.32

Table 3. The table below provides the values of V_{0x} , V_{0y} , α , V_0 and H_{max} parameters calculated based on formulas (1).

Athlete's name	V_{0x} (m/s)	V_{0y} (m/s)	α (degrees)	V_0 (m/s)	H_{max} (m)
Dwight Phillips	8.952	3.451	21.083	9.595	1.777
Irving Saladino	8.454	3.657	23.392	9.211	1.901
Greg Rutherford	9.052	3.124	19.044	9.576	1.777
Jeff Henderson	8.866	3.594	22.067	9.567	1.888
Miltiadis Tentoglou	8.689	3.418	21.476	9.337	1.705

Fig. 5 demonstrates trajectories of the athletes' centres of gravity calculated using the following formulas:

$$X(t) = L_0 + V_{0x} \cdot t - d \cdot (t/T),$$

$$Y(t) = h_0 + V_{0y} \cdot t - g \cdot t^2/2,$$

where t is the time passed from the take-off moment.

Fig. 5. The trajectories of the sportsmen's centres of gravity. The trajectories are numbered according to the tables: 1 - Dwight Phillips, 2 - Irving Saladino, 3 - Greg Rutherford, 4 - Jeff Henderson, 5 - Miltiadis Tentoglou.

It is known that the result of the long jump mainly depends on two parameters - the speed of the athlete's centre of gravity at the take-off moment V_0 , and its angle to the horizontal α . As these parameters increase, the jump result also increases.

Tables 1, 2, and 3 show that the maximum result of 8.59 m belongs to Dwight Phillips, who has the maximum speed at the take-off moment among the five athletes - $V_0 = 9.59$ m/s, and the angle α is 21.083°.

Miltiadis Tentoglou's initial velocity $V_0 = 9.337$ m/s is significantly less than Dwight Phillips' initial velocity, and his jump result is also less - 8.41 m.

Jeff Henderson has quite high values of V_0 and the angle α , but his result of 8.38 m is less than the results of Dwight Phillips and Miltiadis Tentoglou due to the small value of L_0 and the large value of h_2 - 0.14 m and 0.59 m, respectively.

Irving Saladino has the smallest value of V_0 among the five athletes - 9.21 m/s, but his result (8.34 m) is increased by the large value of the landing distance - $L_2 = 0.72$ m.

Greg Rutherford's comparatively low result of 8.31 m is due to the relatively small value of the angle α - 19.04°.

It turns out that our method allows us to find the athlete's strengths and weaknesses, which is very important in the training process.

Conclusions. Based on the conducted research, we can draw the following conclusions:

1. The paper presents an effective method for analysing the long jump, which allows us to find the main parameters of the jump despite the low quality of the video recording.
2. The accuracy of the calculations depends on the quality of the shooting and the frame rate. The higher the frame rate, the higher the accuracy of the analysis.
3. The presented method can be used to analyse both previously recorded videos and pre-planned video recordings. In the second case, it is possible to achieve better quality analysis due to better preparation for video shooting and the use of a better camera.
4. After a minor modification of the calculation algorithm, it is possible to take into account atmospheric effects such as pressure, wind, altitude above sea level, and temperature [4,5,10].

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